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Niḥśreyasa in Pūrva-Mīmāṃsā Gradual Development from Sūtra to Vārttika

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Introduction

Indian philosophy, unique on its part, is an enquiry into the knowledge for a definite purpose. All sorts of philosophical discussions are for the ultimate aim of mokṣa or liberation. Thus, Concept of liberation forms an integral part of Indian Philosophy, all of which irrespective of any categorization have discussed about it. Discussion on the topic of liberation basically involves elaboration on the nature of liberation, the means of liberation and the manner in which liberation is achieved. Though there is no contention on the concept of liberation in Indian philosophies, there are differences with respect to these points. It would be interesting to discover the concept of liberation in Pūrva-Mīmāṃsā (PM) which primarily focusses only on the aspect of dharma. A first hand discussion on prominent authors would be inevitable in order to trace the development of the concept of liberation and the interrelation between them. Although the discussion on nature of the self, forms an integral part of any discussion on the nature of liberation, still it would be seen that a fair idea of the concept can be formed even without indulgence into the nature of the self in PM. Hence, it has not been elaborated.

The philosophy of Pūrva-Mīmāṃsā (PM)

PM can be understood through its first Sūtra : athāto dharma-jñāsā (Jaiminisūtra (JS) 1.1.1). The main purpose of PM is to discuss Dharma, the prime authority of which is the Veda. This system deals with the interpretation of Vedic sentences in order to determine Dharma which mainly stands for the rites or actions prescribed for a definite purpose in the Veda. The scope of this philosophy is limited by the statement of its purpose. It was first aphorized by Jaimini and subsequently commented upon by Śabara (1st Cent. BCE). The explanation of Śabara's bhāṣya was done by Kumarila Bhaṭṭa (7th Cent. CE) and Prabhākara Miśra (7th Cent. CE) resulting in formation of two major schools of thought. Some later authors such as Parthasārathi Miśra (10th Cent. CE) and Khandadeva (17th Century), both following the Bhaṭṭa school, have commented upon the whole system in the adhikaraṇa manner. There are various independent treatises too on particular topics. It would be inevitable to look at these major works with their commentaries and some later ones to talk about concept of liberation in PM.

View of Jaimini

Jaimini, in his aphorisms states nothing regarding liberation. The very purpose of his work is stated as Dharma in the first aphorism mentioned above. Commenting upon the first sūtra, Śabara beautifully summarizes all the topics covered in the twelve chapters as

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dealing with five broad questions: What is dharma? What is its definition? What are its means? What are mere appearing means? And what is its purpose?¹

However, this does not mean that Jaimini did not believe in the concept of liberation. For views under the name of Jaimini, we need to look at other literature. Views of Jaimini regarding the nature of liberation have been stated in the Brahmasūtra of Bādarāyaṇa². Under the discussion on the released soul which has attained brahmaloka, whether it can exist with or without the body according to its likings, the sūtra states : ‘Jaimini asserts the existence of body and sense-organs (after the realization of the qualified Brahman), since the Upaniṣad speaks of option’³. There is another mention of Jaimini regarding the characteristic of the soul that has attained nirguṇa-brahman as : ‘Jaimini says that from references etc. (in the Upaniṣads) (it is evident that the liberated soul) becomes established in the attributes that Brahman has’⁴. But any further discussion is curtailed by the lack of direct reference.

View of Śabara

Śabara too sticks firmly to the sole purpose of the system. Discussion on liberation is not found in the bhāṣya. Ganganath Jha has pointed out the stand of Śabara in the words of Prabhākara as:

“Prabhākara states that Śabara was dealing with the subject of Karma, action, hence he confined himself to what benefits the man addicted to Action, not the man who has washed off his impurities and renounced all the desires and Action. Hence, he has not gone forward to deal with the subject of renunciation and liberation. And this is in strict accordance with what is taught in the Bhagvadgītā to the effect – ‘one should not disturb the idea of people addicted to Action.(Bṛhatipg.56)’⁵

The word mokṣa is not found in the bhāṣya. The word niḥsreyasa is indeed seen a couple of times. However, this is not used in the sense of liberation but for highest fruit of a rite.⁶ And according to Jaimini, the highest of these fruits would be svarga.⁷

View of Kumārila Bhaṭṭa

Kumārila Bhaṭṭa (K.) is the prime authority based on whose discussions the concept of liberation in the system of PM can be derived. Interestingly, even he does not discuss it directly. The whole discussion is seen in his magnum opus the Ślokavārttika(ŚV) under the context of sambandhākṣepaparihāra. wherein there is removal of the objection put forth on the relation of word and its

meaning⁸. It would not be out of place to know the discussion through the context very briefly.

The system of Saṅkhya states that the knowledge of the prakṛti and puruṣa is the cause of liberation. This is because, bondage is due to action, and action is caused out of ignorance(ajñāna). And removal of ignorance is through obtainment of the knowledge, which would cease all bondage-causing-action. K. refutes the view by stating that, if ignorance is to be held as the cause of the production of action, then from the destruction of ignorance could result only non-production of (fresh actions), and not the cessation of the results (of previous actions)⁹. K specifically refutes that knowledge as stated by the Saṅkhya leads to liberation. Because it is neither known by means such as sense-perception, or stated by the Veda¹⁰.

A doubt may be raised regarding the second statement, because passages such as ātmā vā are vijijñāsitavya are indeed found in the Veda. Interestingly, such a famous passage from the Upaniṣad is also interpreted by K in a different way which again indicates the thought process of PM. K states that the said sentence does not indicate liberation, but it is meant for inducing in the rites such as jyotiṣṭoma prescribed by the Veda. The passage simple states that the nature of the soul must be known. Such a knowledge would generate the understanding that soul is something different from the body. Hence, this would further induce a person to perform rites such as jyotiṣṭoma which results in obtainment of svarga. Even the statement na punarāvṛtti¹¹ (there is no returning back) in the said context is also taken as just a eulogy¹².

Nature of Liberation

K goes on to expel other concepts associated with the nature of liberation. K denies that liberation is of the form of enjoyment of happiness (sukhopabhogarūpa). Because, in that case, it would rather be svarga and would be of diminishing nature. Anything which has a cause can never be imperishable¹³.

Hence, according to K, for liberation to be eternal, it can only be of the form of absence (abhāvarūpa) and not if it is of the form of bliss. Nyāyaratnākara (of Pārthasārathimīśra), a commentary on ŚV explains this clearly as: the association with the body is bondage, and the non-association with it is liberation. Hence, the final destruction of the already obtained body, and the non-production of the future ones is liberation¹⁴. Bondage is due to action and it would not reoccur, only because of the

destruction of action. G.N. Jha summarises it as ‘ In fact all total destructions are eternal, deliverance too has been shown to be total destruction of the present body etc.’

Moreover, no negation can ever be an effect of any action. Therefore knowledge, which mimāṃsakas consider to be as an action because it is be acquired, cannot be the cause of liberation which is of eternal nature.

Means of achieving liberation

K states that the absolute non-obtainment of the body for the person who has known the real nature of the self, is possible through absence of accumulation of further (fruit of) action and upon the destruction (basically exhaustion) of the earlier action through the experience(of its fruit)¹⁵.

The body is produced for the sake of enjoyment of the fruit born from actions, and upon the complete exhaustion of it, there remains no cause for it to be produced again.

The Nyāyaratnākara(NR) explains it almost the same except for (interestingly) also stating the nature of self as ananta (endless), ajara (undecaying), amara (undying) and aduḥkha (not possessing any pain).

Though K’s statement equates the absence of action as the non-obtainment of body which is the state of liberation, still the attribute of the person mentioned by him namely jñātātmatattvānām (those who have realised the true nature of self) holds an important position in this discussion. K. seems to include the knowledge of self also in the sum total of causes that leads to liberation. Thus, K does include viveka-jñāna as one of the indirect causes of liberation.

One small doubt is also raised in this context. Since the obtainment of body is the result of the contact of mother and father, how can there be efforts towards its non-obtainment. However, K. states that although the obtainment of body is caused by the contact of mother and father, primarily it requires dharma and adharma (the result of good and evil actions). Hence, contact is not the only cause.

Manner of achieving Liberation

What should a person desirous of liberation do? Should he only acquire the self-knowledge, or there is something else to be done K. does accept that they should obtain the knowledge of the self, but they must not stop there. They must:

i. Not indulge in performance of kāmya (action leading to some fruit) and niṣiddha (prohibited) actions which results in further birth for enjoyment of abhyudaya (prosperity) and pratyavāya (sin) respectively.

ii. Perform the nitya (obligatory) and naimittika (occasionally obligatory) actions, because these are meant for destruction of the already acquired adharma.

iii. Must resort to upāsana (worship, meditation etc.) which is meant for destroying the earlier actions and is a cause(sādhana) of liberation¹⁶.

Though rites such as agnihotra are obligatory but the result in the form of heaven is also stated for it. K addresses this issue and states that only those fruits which are performed for specific desire, leads to them. The stated result is not obtained¹⁷ when there is no desire for it.

Another important discussion in this respect is the discussion on the fruits of self-knowledge. The above non-performance of action is possible only in person having the self-knowledge, hence knowledge of the self is indirectly a cause for liberation. In the words of NR, ‘the one who realises the self as separate from the body, develops an unattachment towards the body and becomes liberated through the observance of the means of liberation’¹⁸, hence, the fruits stated in the respect of self-knowledge is but an eulogy. Kāśikā (Sucarita Miśra), another commentary on the Ślokovārttika summarizes the discusses as ‘ Since all the persons so delivered are also found to be knowing the character of the self, therefore, we must admit that such knowledge is only an indirect auxiliary aid to deliverance, but it cannot be held to be the real direct final cause of deliverance’¹⁹.

Some discussion on Self-knowledge

Self-knowledge according to PM, was stated earlier to be assisting in producing inclination towards rites such as jyotiṣṭoma etc. And later is stated to be an indirect cause of liberation. These aspects have been discussed by NR, which speaks about two kinds of self-knowledge:

i. Knowledge of the soul as distinct from the body²⁰
ii. Knowledge of the soul attained by upāsana (worship and meditation)²¹

K when he states that knowledge has not been enjoined for liberation but it assists in inducing towards performance of actions, refers to the former knowledge. The other one does lead to liberation. In fact K himself has stated in the Tantravārttika²² that the knowledge of the self is both kratvartha (for the purpose of rite) and puruṣārtha (resulting in fruits directly for the person).

This is supported by the passages from the Veda, wherein the knowledge of the soul has been prescribed²³ and both the kinds of results namely abhyudaya²⁴ and niḥśreyas²⁵ is heard about the self-knowledge.

View of Prabhākara(P)

P as Śabara, did not discuss about liberation as he too considers the topic of dharma, which is identified with action in the form of rites, as the sole point of discussion in PM. However, we get some idea regarding the views of this school from prakaraṇa-pañcikā of Śālikanāthamiśra²⁶. Śālikanātha(7th- 8th Cent.) is next in authority to P as he has commented on P as well as written a few independent treatises on the school of P²⁷.

Nature

P views on nature of liberation is almost similar to K. P believes that the soul is born with body only because of dharma and adharma. Thus, liberation of the soul consists in disappearance of all dharma and adharma after which there is no obtainment of the body for the soul.

Manner

G.N.Jha has summarised the whole process of liberation in the views of P²⁸. To quote, ‘When a person becomes disgusted with the troubles, he starts finding even the pleasures of the world as accompanied by some sort of pain and he turns his attention towards liberation. He ceases to perform such deeds as are prohibited, and also those which lead to some sort of happiness. He attenuates all previous dharma and adharma by undergoing experience resulting from them. He destroys the sole receptacle or abode of his experience by the knowledge of the soul, along with auxiliaries such as contentment, self-control etc. which are all laid down in the scriptures²⁹ to put stop to further return of the soul’. Pt. Subrahmanya Shastri³⁰ in his comments upon the combined cause of knowledge and action towards liberation has discussed two kinds of samuccaya and concludes that the two are combined equally here. There is no subservience of one towards the other, because there is no pramāṇa to establish that one serves the purpose of the other.

Comparison of K. and P.

Thus, we find that the views of P are similar to K in considering the negative character of liberation as destruction of the present body and non-obtainment of any further body³¹.

The only difference lies in non-acceptance of the eulogistic quality of the sentence na punarāvartate by P. Śālikanātha states that the knowledge of the self is not subservient to anything else, hence the fruit stated in its context cannot be regarded as arthavāda³².

Conclusion

It is interesting to note the gradual development of discussions from sūtra to vārttika. The topic of niḥśreyasa

which almost lies untouched in the sūtra is gradually dealt with in details in the later literature which may have developed out of interaction among philosophies. This gradual development of discussion is also indicative of development of Pūrva-Mīmāṃsā as a system of philosophy.

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- ¹ को धर्मः ? कथं लक्षणः ? कानि साधनानि ? कानि साधनाभासानि ? किं परश्च ? (Śābarabhāṣya on JS 1.1.1)
 - ² It is believed in tradition that Jaimini was one of the disciples of Bādarāyaṇa. The name of Bādarāyaṇa also appears in the Jaimini Sūtra 1.1.5.
 - ³ भावं जैमिनिः, विकल्पामननात् 4.4.11. (This is projected as a view against that of Bādari who states, अभावं बादरिः आह ह्येवम् BrahmaSūtra 4.4.10). (Gambhirananda : 1977)
 - ⁴ ब्राह्मेण जैमिनिः, उपन्यासादिभ्यः BrahmaSū. 4.4.5 (Gambhirananda : 1977)
- The whole context of the discussion is with respect to the two aspects of liberated soul namely i. pure intelligence, and ii. Conditioned aspect of Brahman. The earlier ascribed to Audulomi and the latter to Jaimini.
- ⁵ Jha, G.N. *Purva Mimamsa in its Sources*, pg. 31.
 - ⁶ यः पुरुषं निःश्रेयसेन संयुनक्ति स धर्मशब्देनोच्यते ... यः निःश्रेयसाय ज्योतिष्टोमादिः Śabara on JS. 1.1.2.
 - ⁷ सः स्वर्गः स्यात् सर्वान्प्रति अविशिष्टत्वात् JS. 4.3.7
 - ⁸ Relationship of word and meaning is discussed under JS. 1.1.5
 - ⁹ Sambandhākṣepaparihāra(SP.) 101. (under ŚV. on JS 1.1.5)
 - ¹⁰ SP. 102
 - ¹¹ Chandogyopaniṣad 8.15.1.
 - ¹² See JS. 4.3.1, any fruit stated in relation to a substance, *saṃskāra* and action is taken to be a eulogy, since all the three are meant for something else.
 - ¹³ न हि कारणवत् किञ्चिदक्षयित्वेन गम्यते SP. 106.
 - ¹⁴ शरीरसम्बन्धो बन्धः, तदभावो मोक्षः । तेन निष्पन्नानां देहानां यः प्रध्वंसाभावः यश्चानुत्पन्नानां प्रागभावः स मोक्षः on SP. 106
 - ¹⁵ तत्र ज्ञातात्मतत्त्वानां भोगात्पूर्वक्रियाक्षये । उत्तरप्रचयासत्त्वाद्देहो नोत्पद्यते पुनः SP. 108
 - ¹⁶ This is supported in Nyāyaratnākara by quoting the verse of Bhagavadgītā as ज्ञानाग्निः सर्वकर्माणि भस्मसात् कुरुते तथा BG. 4.37.
 - ¹⁷ प्रार्थ्यमानं फलं ज्ञातं न चानिच्छोर्भविष्यति SV. 111
 - ¹⁸ देहविकृतात्मज्ञान एव हि देहसम्बन्धे वैराग्यात् यथोक्तमोक्षोपायानुष्ठानेन मुक्तो भवतीति तदालम्बोऽर्थवादः

¹⁹ On ŚV. 108 (pg. 367, Jha : 79)

- ²⁰ Known by passages such as अविनाशी वा अरे आत्मा (Bṛhadāraṇyakopaniṣad 4.5.14)
- ²¹ आत्मानमुपासीत (Bṛhadāraṇyakopaniṣad 1.4.8)
- ²² आत्मज्ञानं हि संयोगपृथक्त्वात् क्रत्वर्थपुरुषार्थत्वेन ज्ञायते, तेन विना परलोकफलेषु कर्मसु प्रवृत्तिनिवृत्त्यसम्भवात् Tantravārttika on 1.3.27 (pg. 227).
- ²³ य आत्माऽपहतपाप्मा विजरो विमृत्युर्विशोको विजिवत्सोऽपिपासः सत्यसंकल्पः सोऽन्वेष्टव्यः स विजिज्ञासितव्यः (Chandogyopaniṣad 8.8.1), also आत्मा वा अरे... मन्तव्य बोद्धव्यः (Bṛhadāraṇyakopaniṣad 4.5.6), also आत्मानमुपासीत (ibid. 1.4.8)
- ²⁴ स सर्वाश्च लोकान् आप्नोति, सर्वाश्च कामान् आप्नोति, तरति शोकम् आत्मवित् (Chandogyopaniṣad 7.1.3)
- ²⁵ स खलु एनं वर्तयन्वावदायुषं ब्रह्मलोकम् अभिसंपद्यते न स पुनरावर्तते (Chandogyopaniṣad 8.15.1)
- ²⁶ Śālikanātha is believed to be a direct disciple of Prabhākara.
- ²⁷ For detailed treatise on Prabhākara school, refer to ‘*The Prabhākara School of Pūrva-Mīmāṃsā*’ by Ganganatha Jha.
- ²⁸ *The Prabhākara School of Pūrva-Mīmāṃsā*, pg. 83.
- ²⁹ शम-दम-ब्रह्मचर्यादि-अङ्गोपबृंहितेन आत्मज्ञानेन न पुनरावृत्तये चोदितेन निश्शेषकर्माशयं नाशयन् मुच्यते pg. 341
- ³⁰ Footnote 3, Pg. 341 (Shastri :1961)
- ³¹ आत्यन्तिकस्तु देहोच्छेदो निःशेषधर्माधर्मपरिक्षयनिबन्धनो मोक्षः इति युक्तम् धर्माधर्मवशीकृतो हि जीवस्तासु तासु योनिषु संसरति स तयोः एकान्तोच्छेदे व्यपगतदेहेन्द्रिसम्बन्धस्समुत्खातनिखिलसांसारिकदुःखानुबन्धो मुक्त इत्युच्यते (प्रकरणपञ्चिका(मोक्षवादः) pg. 341)
- ³² आत्मज्ञानस्यापारार्थता । परार्थत्वे हि पर्णमयीन्यायेन फलश्रुतिरर्थवादतया वर्ण्येत । ज्ञानविधेरपारार्थ्ये तु सैव (अपुनरावृत्तिः) अधिकारिविशेषणं रात्रिसत्रवत् । प्रकरणपञ्चिका (मोक्षवादः) pg. 343.